

Possible Antituberculous Compounds. Part XIV. Condensation Products of Hydrazides and Isonitroso Ketones

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Twentyeight new compounds have been synthesised by condensing different hydrazides and isonitroso ketones with a view to studying their tuberculostatic activity.

Since the discovery of the antitubercular property of isonicotinoyl hydrazide, numerous aliphatic, aromatic, and heterocyclic hydrazides have been prepared and tested by different workers. Buu-Hôï *et al.*¹ condensed various aldehydes and ketones with hydrazides with a view to blocking the free amino function in the hydrazides and thus they obtained compounds with lower toxicity. Likewise, Misra and Khare² prepared a number of cresotinic acid hydrazides and their condensation products with aldehydes³ and of these, *N*-2-hydroxybenzylidene-cresotinic acid hydrazide inhibited the growth of *Mycobacterium tubercule* in dilutions to 1:40,000.

Recently, Giammanco³ condensed various hydrazides with isonitroso ketones to obtain products of biological interest by virtue of the presence of the $-\text{CONHN}=\text{C}-$ group and the $=\text{NOH}$ group which impart antiparasitic, fungicidal, and bactericidal properties to such compounds.

This work has now been extended by synthesising various hydrazides and condensing them with different isonitroso ketones. The final condensation was effected by refluxing the two components in 95% ethanol. The compounds obtained are recorded in Table I. The antitubercular activity of these compounds will be reported later on.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isonitroso ketones were prepared by the method of Hartung *et al.*⁴ and crystallised from ethanol. The hydrazides were prepared by adding hydrazine hydrate (100%) dropwise to a boiling ethanolic solution of the methyl ester of the desired acids; the reaction mixture was refluxed for 4 to 5 hours and after cooling the product was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Condensation of the isonitroso ketones with the hydrazides was carried out by refluxing their equimolar quantities in 95% ethanol for 2 to 4 hours. The product was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 1958.
2. *This Journal*, 1954, 31, 323.
3. *Ann. Chim.*, 1961, 51, 175.
4. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 57, 176.

TABLE I

No.	Hydrazides.	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Req.
A. Isonitroso-acetophenone.						
1.	Benzoic	170°	85%	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₃	15.56	15.73
2.	Salicylic	182°	96	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃	15.12	14.84
3.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzoic	241°	95	"	14.68	"
4.	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic	238°	35	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₄	18.24	17.94
5.	<i>p</i> -Cresotic	*208-10°	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃	14.46	14.14
6.	<i>o</i> -Cresotic	183°	90	"	14.32	"
7.	Phenylacetic	110-15°	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃	14.54	14.94
B. Isonitroso- <i>p</i> -methylacetophenone.						
1.	Benzoic	226°	95	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₃	14.62	14.94
2.	Salicylic	220-24°	96	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ O ₃ N ₃	14.34	14.14
3.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzoic	253-54°	95	"	14.42	"
4.	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic	249°	40	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₄	17.52	17.17
5.	<i>p</i> -Cresotic	222°	55	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ O ₃ N ₃	13.36	13.50
6.	Isoniazid	*210-12°	80	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄	19.45	19.85
C. Isonitroso- <i>p</i> -chloro-acetophenone.						
1.	Benzoic	237°	99	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	14.56	13.93
2.	Salicylic	215°	100	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	13.56	13.22
3.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzoic	222°	80	"	13.64	"
4.	<i>p</i> -Cresotic	255-57°	98	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	12.32	12.66
5.	<i>o</i> -Cresotic	184°	90	"	12.46	"
6.	Isoniazid	113°	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	18.38	18.51
7.	Phenylacetic	154-55°	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	12.98	13.31
D. Isonitroso- <i>p</i> -chloropropiophenone.						
1.	Benzoic	211°	85	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	13.52	13.31
2.	Salicylic	165-68°	95	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	12.44	12.66
3.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzoic	216°	96	"	12.34	"
4.	<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic	209°	30	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	16.10	15.53
5.	<i>p</i> -Cresotic	178°	98	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ N ₃ Cl	12.82	12.51
6.	<i>o</i> -Cresotic	191°	98	"	12.68	"
7.	Isoniazid	152-53°	70	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	18.14	17.89
8.	Phenylacetic	230°	45	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₃ Cl	13.42	13.04

*Decompose on heating.

Thanks of the authors are due to Professor A. B. Sen for his helpful discussions during the period of investigation.